

Energy Retrofit Potential in the Public Housing Stock: the case of Catania

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the energy performance of a series of public housing buildings constructed between the 1950s and the 1990s with reinforced concrete structures, very common in those decades. The buildings are located in Catania, a large city in Southern Italy with around 5,000 public housing apartments. Apart from providing a picture of the current energy quality of public housing in Italy, the study also investigates the energy saving potential of innovative energy retrofit solutions with prefabricated insulated wooden panels, under development in the H2020 project “e-SAFE”, coordinated by the University of Catania. According to this investigation, they allow for primary energy savings above 85% for space heating, and between 75% and 80% including cooling and Domestic Hot Water. However, not all e-SAFE solutions are suitable for every building: the investigation suggests they can be applied to around 37% of the public housing stock, which would guarantee around 30% of total primary energy savings.

KEYWORDS

Public housing; energy performance; reinforced concrete; prefabricated wooden panels; energy renovation.

INTRODUCTION

The current environmental scenario presents challenges such as ecological transition, sustainability and carbon emissions reduction: in this framework, the building sector has a key role and requires radical actions to improve its energy and environmental performance. Considering the current very low yearly construction rate, between 75% and 85% of the existing buildings in the EU would still be in use in 2050 [1]: this suggests that current and future policies should mainly address existing buildings, which require deep renovation to significantly reduce their non-renewable primary energy consumption.

In this framework, the paper focuses on the energy performance of the public housing stock, which makes up a non-negligible portion of the residential stock in Italian cities. To analyse the current state of the public housing assets, the paper studies the energy performance of a series of residential buildings constructed between the 1950s and the 1990s. This specific period, ranging from the reconstruction period after World War II and the implementation of the first stringent energy efficiency measures for buildings, was chosen because it features very poor thermal performance of the residential stock. All the investigated buildings have reinforced concrete structures, very common in those decades, and are located in Catania, a large city in

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Southern Italy with more than 300,000 inhabitants and around 5,000 public housing apartments belonging to the Autonomous Institute of Public Housing (IACP), corresponding to more than 3% of the city's residential stock. Furthermore, a statistical analysis of the residential stock at national level verified the relevance and representativeness of the selected buildings: in fact, concrete-framed buildings constructed between the 1950s and 1990 account for 40% of the public housing stock in Italy [2].

The energy performance of such buildings has been evaluated through quasi-stationary calculations as required for Energy Certification purposes in Italy and is based on accurate surveys of building envelope and technical systems. Then, the study investigates the energy saving potential of some innovative retrofit solutions with prefabricated insulated wooden panels that can also provide improved seismic performance: these solutions are being developed and demonstrated in the H2020 project "e-SAFE", coordinated by the University of Catania, and can potentially pave the way towards a massive combined energy and seismic renovation of the residential building stock. Thus, the paper aims at identifying the effectiveness of these solutions not only at single building scale, but also their possible penetration in a significant urban area as well as the consequent decarbonization potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper, representative buildings of the public housing stock in Catania are first identified as case study buildings and described with their main geometric and thermal features. Then, the e-SAFE project renovation solutions are reported and their application to the case study buildings is discussed. Finally, the achieved energy performance is analysed in detail and contrasted against those achieved in the current buildings' state.

The energy performance has been appraised through quasi-stationary calculations carried out according to the current Italian Norms for the Energy Certification of buildings [3]. Accordingly, the employed key performance indicators (KPIs) include the energy needs for space heating ($EP_{H,nd}$) and the total non-renewable primary energy consumption for heating, cooling and DHW services ($EP_{gl,nren}$). Such KPIs have been estimated through the commercial software tool Termus for the current state of the buildings: Termus is compliant with the Italian Standard UNI 11300:1 and uses a quasi-steady-state approach relying on monthly energy balances in standard conditions [3-4].

Instead, energy retrofit performance was assessed by the innovative decision support tool e-DSS. This tool is being developed within the H2020 e-SAFE project and aims at guiding the technicians and the building owners to the choice of the most suitable renovation solution amongst those envisaged by the e-SAFE portfolio [5]. It can calculate parameters such as CO₂ emissions due to buildings' operation and the expected costs and time for their renovation, as well as the energy performance based on a simplified, yet reliable quasi-steady-state energy balance approach described in the European Norm EN ISO 13790:2008 [6]. Both Termus and e-DSS require user input regarding building geometry, envelope thermal properties and technical systems, while the climate data is retrieved by the Italian Norm UNI 10349-1 [7]. Regarding the city of Catania – where all the investigated buildings are located – it belongs to Italian Climate Zone B, which includes all the cities with heating degree days (HDD) between 600 and 900. For these cities, Italian laws dictate a heating period from December 1 to March 31 [8]. For the city of Catania, the design conditions for winter are $T = 5\text{ °C}$ and $RH = 60\%$ whereas in summer are $T = 33.6\text{ °C}$ and $RH = 48\%$.

Description of the investigated buildings

This study has considered four residential buildings, belonging to the local Autonomous Institute of Public Housing (IACP), to investigate the energy performance of the current public residential building stock in Catania. Their period of construction spans from 1959 to 2006, and they are placed in four different districts: San Leone (Via Aurora), Nesima (Via Cantone), Acquicella (Via Acquicella) and Librino (Viale Nitta). These districts belong to the south-western side of Catania, which has been the theatre of a rapid city expansion since 1950s: apart from Acquicella, the other districts have a very high building density with poor services, and a high number of residential public buildings. Acquicella is an anomalous district, since it hosts just one very degraded residential complex surrounded by abandoned industrial complexes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Pictures of the four investigated buildings.

Table 1 reports the main geometric and thermal features of the investigated buildings. These data derive from official project documentations available in the archives of IACP, supported by detailed surveys carried out by the authors. Table 1 also underlines that the selected districts include many buildings identical to those here described, as it usually happens in case of public residential housing: this suggests that the results of this study are relevant to a significant portion of IACP building stock. The building in Via Acquicella is also the pilot building that is going to be renovated within the H2020 e-SAFE project.

All buildings have reinforced concrete structures, and cavity walls with two layers of clay bricks (Viale Nitta, Via Cantone) or concrete blocks (Via Acquicella, Via Aurora). The buildings in Viale Nitta were completed in 2006: however, their design and the related building permits dates to 1996,

hence they are representative of design criteria in force in the 1990s, when the opaque envelope components were already provided with low thermal insulation (40 mm EPS in the cavity, in this case). Regarding the windows, in some cases the original ones have already been replaced with more performing double glazing by the residents, which justifies the differences amongst the various buildings, not entirely correlated with the construction period. It is worth noting that the four buildings have different ratios between outer heated surface and gross heated volume (S/V); indeed, Via Aurora has a compact shape, leading to a low $S/V = 0.34$, while the other buildings have a less regular shape with many protruding volumes, thus yielding $S/V = 0.45 \div 0.52$. The highest value pertains to Via Cantone, due to the low number of floors that emphasizes the role of the roof and the ground slab.

Amongst the parameters reported in Table 1, H'_T is the overall heat transfer coefficient of the entire envelope, that is calculated through a weighted average of the various U-values and including thermal bridging effects. According to the Italian Decree of 26/06/2015 [9], reporting the “Minimum Criteria” holding in case of new constructions and energy renovations, this parameter must comply with the following thresholds, referred to Climate Zone B:

- $H'_T < 0.80 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ if $S/V < 0.4 \text{ m}^{-1}$ (like in Via Aurora)
- $H'_T < 0.63 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ if $0.4 \leq S/V < 0.7 \text{ m}^{-1}$ (like in all other buildings)

Since for all the investigated buildings these conditions are by far not met, this demonstrates that their energy performance is deceiving, and that their envelope needs substantial insulation to become in line with the current energy requirements in Italy.

Coming to the thermal systems for space heating and DHW preparation, these are not strictly correlated to the construction period: indeed, residents are likely to replace them quite frequently. The survey allowed verifying that all buildings rely on autonomous systems, whereas no centralized heating systems are used. On the one hand, in Viale Nitta and Via Cantone all dwellings use gas boilers to provide both space heating and DHW. On the other hand, in Via Acquicella and Via Aurora space heating is mostly provided through electric split units; however, some dwellings are not equipped with space heating systems. In these two buildings DHW is mostly provided through small electric boilers – typically 1.2 kW electric power – but some dwellings rely on gas boilers. Space cooling is available only in those dwellings equipped with split units.

Table 1. Comparison between the main geometric and thermal features

	Via Aurora	Via Acquicella	Via Cantone	Viale Nitta
Year of construction	1959	1964	1972	1996
Number of heated floors	7	5	4	8
Number of dwellings	28	10	8	32
Heated surface (m²)	1835	940	725	2065
Similar buildings in the district	3	11	17	10
S/V ratio (m⁻¹)	0.34	0.47	0.52	0.45
U-value: walls (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)	1.17	0.99	1.11	0.50
U-value: roof (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)	1.36	1.19	2.03	0.51
U-value: ground floor (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)	1.55	0.65	1.82	0.55
U-value: windows (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)	6.12	3.90	6.00	3.10
H'_T (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)	2.12	1.67	1.71	1.26
Mean global efficiency for heating	2.57	0.74	0.54	0.56
Mean global efficiency for DHW	0.35	0.29	0.48	0.40

Table 2. Type and number of available thermal systems for heating and DHW preparation.

Decade	Space heating system			DHW system	
	Split units	Gas boiler	No heating	Gas boiler	Electric boiler
1990s	–	32	–	32	–
1970s	–	8	–	8	–
1960s	8	–	2	1	9
1950s	20	–	8	4	24

Description of the e-SAFE technologies

The e-SAFE project proposes three innovative technological components – namely e-PANEL, e-CLT and e-EXOS – that, adequately combined, ensure energy, seismic and architectural renovation of existing buildings with reinforced concrete structures.

The e-PANEL consists of prefabricated plug-and-play panels made of a timber-framed structure combined with local bio-based recyclable/recycled insulation and finished by the desired cladding material. In earthquake-prone countries, the e-PANEL can be applied to the vertical walls that include openings, while the blind walls will be covered by a different type of panels called e-CLT (Figure 2): this is made of prefabricated Cross Laminated Timber (CLT) boards equipped with seismic energy dissipation devices. The e-CLT panel is also completed by an external insulation layer and by the desired finishing material. Always in seismic areas, in addition to or in place of e-CLT, the e-SAFE envelope system includes e-EXOS, which is an ensemble of external metal bracings equipped with seismic dampers (Figure 1). e-EXOS is installed on the outside of the existing building and does not interrupt the continuous layer realized by e-CLT and/or e-PANEL. Further details about the technical features of the e-SAFE solutions can be found in previous publications [10-12]. It is here useful to underline that, at the current state of the research and development activities, some limitations have emerged that may reduce the applicability of these solutions. For instance, e-CLT and e-EXOS cannot be used when:

- The building is subject to constraints that prevent changing its appearance (e.g., local regulations, historical and cultural heritage);
- The building has more than six stories above ground, since in this case the panels would put too much weight on the existing reinforced concrete structure;
- There is no sufficient space for crane operations around the building, which is a problem because these panels are erected from the outside without the need for scaffolding;
- There is no sufficient space to install the exoskeleton in case e-EXOS is used;
- The building has more than two facades attached to other buildings (in this case the potential for energy and seismic improvement would be too small);
- There is a high number of balconies around the building, and/or a high area of openings on the ground floor (less than 60% of the total envelope area on the ground floor).

These limitations have an impact on the potential of e-SAFE renovation to decarbonize the existing public residential building stock. The first condition, in the case of public buildings, can always be considered fulfilled since this type of building has commonly no historical or cultural value and their construction, in co-partnership or with direct public action, does not violate local regulations. The other conditions should be evaluated case by case. The Decision Support System (e-DSS) developed within e-SAFE allows understanding whether the e-SAFE renovation solutions are applicable, and guides the user to the selection of the most appropriate combination.

Coming to the thermal systems, the e-THERM architecture proposed in e-SAFE relies on centralized electricity-driven air-to-water heat pumps and roof-mounted PV panels for on-site electricity generation. To make full profit of PV-based electricity production, e-THERM

appoints a central role to heat storage: a first storage level is provided by large, centralized water tanks, and the system is equipped with a programmable control to use the water tanks as a buffer and let the heat pump operate in the most convenient conditions. The second level of thermal energy storage is provided by innovative thin and modular decentralized tanks, called hereafter e-TANK, primarily devoted to DHW storage. The e-TANK is the “intelligent” core that includes a hydraulic unit with mechanical components to distribute hot and cold water to the fan coil units (valves, manifolds, pipe connectors) and control devices to manage the system operation according to specific control logics, while also monitoring temperatures and energy consumption for both heating and DHW [13].

Figure 2. e-SAFE technologies considered in this study [12]: (a) e-CLT and e-PANEL; (b) e-EXOS and e-PANEL; (c) e-THERM architecture; (d) e-TANK.

Description of the proposed retrofit solutions

In this study, energy and seismic building renovation relies on the combination of e-PANEL and e-CLT, according to the principles explained in the previous section. The first step of the retrofit design consists in identifying the minimum thickness of insulation needed to comply with the national regulations, which in climate zone B set $U < 0.40 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for external walls and $U < 0.32 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for roofs. Table 3 reports the results of this preliminary analysis, where wood fibre is used as insulating material ($\lambda = 0.038 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$). As expected, the buildings designed according to 1990s rules – in Viale Nitta – require a lower thickness of insulation than for the other buildings during the renovation stage. Coming to the windows, a new type of fixtures was assigned to all the buildings under investigation: they consist of double glazing with low-E deposit and an aluminium frame with thermal break, whose thermal transmittance is $U = 1.7 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. The solar factor assumed for the calculations is $g = 0.67$.

Table 3. Thermal insulation applied in the energy renovation of the various buildings.

	Walls insulation		Roof insulation	
	Thickness	U-value	Thickness	U-value
Via Aurora (1950s)	120 mm	0.37 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹	100 mm	0.31 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹
Via Acquicella (1960s)	120 mm	0.37 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹	100 mm	0.32 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹
Via Cantone (1970s)	120 mm	0.37 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹	100 mm	0.32 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹
Viale Nitta (1990s)	80 mm	0.39 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹	80 mm	0.30 W·m ⁻² ·K ⁻¹

The solutions adopted to replace the thermal systems are the same in all the investigated buildings and reflect the e-THERM architecture described in the previous paragraph. The centralised reversible air-to-water heat pump has COP = 3.8 at 35 °C reference supply temperature in the heating season, and EER = 3.0 at 7 °C reference supply temperature in the cooling season. The average seasonal performance of the heat pump for DHW preparation is estimated as COP = 2.5, since DHW is provided at higher temperature than space heating. Three fan coils per apartment are set up as terminals for the air conditioning system (emission efficiency = 0.95). On the other hand, the control system is managed at room level with climate compensation (control efficiency = 0.97). The e-TANK, i.e. the storage tanks for DHW purposes, are well insulated and keep energy losses to only 10% of the delivered energy; further thermal losses are accounted for in the well-insulated secondary distribution lines (2%). In this study, no PV systems were included in the renovation design: indeed, this would add too many variables and would introduce significant differences between taller buildings (Viale Nitta, Via Aurora) and smaller ones (Via Cantone, Via Acquicella), where the PV surface is more favourable in proportion to the number of dwellings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Energy performance of the investigated buildings: before energy retrofit

The following graphs provide information about the statistical distribution of the KPIs in the various buildings. To this purpose "boxplots" are used: they allow showing the data distribution while identifying the first and the third quartiles (the bottom and top borders of the boxes), as well as the minimum and maximum values (the bottom and the top horizontal segments); the "x" and the horizontal segment inside the boxes are respectively the mean and the median value. Finally, outliers are indicated with dots outside the boxes.

Figure 3 shows the statistical distribution of EP_{H,nd} for each building. It is easy to understand that the older the building, the higher the EP_{H,nd} value: indeed, the poorer quality of the building envelope implies higher energy losses. The box belonging to Viale Nitta is very narrow (between 12 and 20 kWh·m⁻² per year): indeed, in this case all opaque envelope components (roof, walls, and ground floor) are equally insulated and show similar U-value (see Table 1), thus reducing the differences between dwellings in different floors and with different exposure. It is also worth highlighting that the box belonging to Via Acquicella is narrower than in Via Cantone, and has a lower third quartile: this happens because of the very high U-value of roof and ground floor in Via Cantone (see Table 1), which therefore increases EP_{H,nd} for the apartments in the first and last floor. However, the median values in both buildings are similar, suggesting that – on average – no great difference holds between residential public buildings built in the 1960s and the 1970s in Catania. Via Aurora is the oldest building and shows the highest final energy needs for space heating: the interquartile range is between 40 and 80 kWh·m⁻² per year, but the dwellings in the last floor reach 110 kWh·m⁻² per year. Figure 4 shows the details of the energy needs for space heating by exposure and by floor where the dwelling is located, with reference – as an example – to Via Aurora. In general, it can be observed that the apartments in the first floor always show a lower average EP_{H,nd} than in the top floor, by about 25-30%. EP_{H,nd} can also be correlated to the

main exposure: in fact, dwellings with exposures including the south have a thermal energy requirement that is from 25% to 50% lower than those facing north, for any given floor. Dwellings facing west also show lower energy needs than those facing east, the difference ranging from 5% to 10%.

Figure 3. Statistical distributions of the final thermal energy need for space heating.

Figure 4. Energy needs for space heating in Via Aurora (1950s): detailed values per dwelling.

Figure 5. Statistical distributions of the total non-renewable primary energy consumption (Heating + DHW + Cooling).

Coming to the non-renewable primary energy consumption, Figure 5 reflects the trends already highlighted in Figure 3 for space heating. However, Figure 5 also includes the contribution of the

other services: here, a significant role is played by Domestic Hot Water preparation, whose primary energy consumption is strongly affected by the type of heat generator used to this scope and by its estimated efficiency, which were already presented in Table 1 and Table 2. On the one hand, when the prevalent DHW generator is the electric boiler, like in Via Acquicella and Via Aurora, the mean global efficiency for DHW preparation lies around 30%, which corresponds to a non-renewable primary energy consumption ranging from 40 to 50 kWh·m⁻² per year. On the other hand, gas boilers ensure mean global efficiency above 40%, and an annual non-renewable primary energy consumption of around 30 kWh·m⁻². Overall, the worst performing building is the oldest one (Via Aurora, 1950s) with an interquartile range for EP_{gl,nren} between 80 and 150 kWh·m⁻²; on the contrary, the most recent building (Viale Nitta, 1990s) shows the best overall performance with a narrow interquartile range for EP_{gl,nren} (between 52 and 70 kWh·m⁻²).

Accordingly, the apartments in Viale Nitta can be classified either in Class C or in Class D (Fig. 6); in the other buildings the predominant energy Classes are E, F and G, apart from Via Aurora, showing a variety of energy classes. Via Aurora is a quite peculiar case: the best energy classes refer to intermediate floors where the compact shape limits heat losses (more specifically, Class B occur in those apartments that rely on natural gas boilers for DHW preparation), whereas the apartments in the ground and last floor fall in Class F.

Figure 6. Statistical distributions of the classes resulting in the Energy Performance Certificates.

Energy performance of the investigated buildings: after building retrofit

The comparison between the energy performance before and after the proposed e-SAFE renovation solutions is performed by looking at the average values for the entire buildings. Indeed, the e-DSS tool is not able to investigate the energy performance of the single apartments. Table 4 shows that the proposed level of thermal insulation for both opaque and transparent envelope components is sufficient to match, even if with little distance, the maximum overall heat transfer coefficient set by the Italian Decree of 26/06/2015 (0.8 W·m⁻²·K⁻¹ in Via Aurora, 0.63 W·m⁻²·K⁻¹ in the other buildings). This means that more effective renovation solutions might be conceived, albeit at a higher cost for the public housing institute.

The significant energy savings ensured by the e-SAFE renovation are evident from the results reported in Table 5 and Figure 7. Heating is the service where it is possible to get the highest reduction in the non-renewable primary energy consumption (from 87% to 95%), the lowest value referring to the most recent and already slightly insulated building (Viale Nitta). Domestic Hot Water preparation shows potential primary energy savings in the range of 69% to 77%, thanks to the replacement of the outdated gas and electric boilers with modern and efficient air-to-water heat pumps, together with an appropriate insulation of piping and storage tanks. Finally, space cooling shows a limited potential for primary energy savings (from 32% to 48%). Overall, the total non-renewable primary energy needs decrease by 70% to 80%, thus providing “deep” energy renovation; all buildings can now be classified in Class A. Further improvements can be achieved by adding a roof-mounted PV system, but this is not the scope of this paper.

Table 4. Overall heat transfer coefficient (H_T) attained after e-SAFE renovation.

Viale Nitta	Via Cantone	Via Acquicella	Via Aurora
$0.62 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$	$0.61 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$	$0.62 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$	$0.75 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$

Table 5. Average values of the non-renewable primary energy consumption for the different services (H: heating; C: cooling; W: domestic hot water). All values are in $\text{kWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ per year.

	Before e-SAFE retrofit				After e-SAFE retrofit			
	H	C	DHW	Total	H	C	DHW	Total
Viale Nitta (1990s)	56.7	23.7	42.7	123.1	7.0	15.6	13.3	35.9
Via Cantone (1970s)	88.3	20.0	37.3	57.3	5.9	13.6	8.8	28.3
Via Acquicella (1960s)	76.2	26.4	48.0	150.6	4.9	13.7	11.8	30.4
Via Aurora (1950s)	80.8	36.4	53.6	170.8	4.1	20.8	13.2	38.1

Figure 7. Non-renewable primary energy savings allowed by the proposed retrofit solutions.

Potential impact of the e-SAFE renovation scheme

According to the latest ISTAT statistics published in 2011 [2], in the municipality of Catania there are 144,577 residential units, and 542,148 in the entire province. Their distribution in the various construction periods is reported in Table 6. Looking only at the public residential buildings, the available units are 4,748 in the only municipality and 8,306 in the entire province, corresponding respectively to 3.0% and 1.5% of the building stock. Since the e-SAFE retrofit solutions are suitable only for non-historical and non-listed buildings with RC structures, we have first excluded from our analysis the buildings built before 1946 (since they are most probably without RC structure, and in many cases listed) and those built after 2000 (since they are reasonably not in need of energy and seismic retrofit). The remaining buildings (1946-2000) are 78.7% of the building stock in the province; however, by using also statistical data provided by ISI-Federcasa that report information about the type of building envelope, it was possible to understand that this percentage decreases to 47% of the residential public building stock if one excludes the buildings without RC structure.

Table 6. Statistics regarding the residential building stock in Catania [2]

Construction period	Before 1918	1918-1945	1946-1960	1961-1970	1971-1980	1981-1990	1991-2000	After 2000
Entire province	31,147	54,088	81,738	101,972	118,101	82,445	42,631	30,026
Municipality	14,222	24,340	31,309	28,710	25,718	13,394	5,021	1,863

Now, if one extends to these buildings the primary energy savings determined in this study and reported in Table 5, the entire public residential building stock might reduce by 37.4% its primary energy consumption. However, the implementation of the e-SAFE envelope solutions is limited by the number of floors and by some further boundary conditions, as explained in the previous sections. If one considers these limitations, around 1/4 of the IACP building stock is not suitable for e-SAFE, and the potential primary energy savings achieved through e-SAFE renovation for the entire IACP stock goes down to 27.5%.

CONCLUSION

This study has highlighted the low energy performance of the residential public building stock in Catania, which is however representative of the Italian one. The non-renewable primary energy consumption can be easily correlated with the construction period, and the results allow identifying median values and interquartile ranges for the various decades from 1950s to 1990s. More in details, the thermal energy needs for space heating also depend on the floor and the exposure of the single dwellings; instead, the annual primary energy needs for DHW preparation – ranging from 30 to 50 kWh·m⁻² – cannot be correlated with the construction period, but mainly depend on the type of boilers that have been installed. Overall, the potential for energy retrofit in this building stock is enormous; the proposed e-SAFE technological solutions allow cutting by 70% to 80% the total non-renewable primary energy on a single building, thus providing “deep” energy renovation. However, since e-SAFE solutions only apply to less than 40% of the building stock, their overall potential energy savings for the entire IACP stock has been assessed around 27.5%.

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NOMENCLATURE

C: Cooling
COP: Coefficient of Performance (-)
DHW: Domestic Hot Water
EER: Energy Efficiency Ratio (-)
H: Heating
HDD: Heating Degree Days (°C·days)
H_T: Overall heat transfer coefficient (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)
PV: Photovoltaic
RC: Reinforced Concrete
S: overall surface area of the heated building envelope (m²)
U: thermal transmittance (W·m⁻²·K⁻¹)
V: gross heated volume (m³)
λ: thermal conductivity (W·m⁻¹·K⁻¹)

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